

An evidence-informed commentary on animal experimentation regulation and the development of alternative methods in six Latin American countries

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Abstract

Background: Animal experimentation remains part of biomedical research, toxicology, agriculture, education, and product safety assessment in Latin America, while the development and implementation of alternative methods are advancing unevenly. Regulatory frameworks regarding animal use for experimentation differ across countries, and limited public reporting often prevents a clear understanding of the number of animals used, the species involved, and the procedures performed.

Aim and scope: This evidence-informed commentary examines the regulation of animal experimentation and the development of alternative methods in six Latin American countries where Te Protejo, a civil society organization, through its work in awareness raising, public policy and community engagement, has established institutional presence and regional experience; Chile, Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Peru, and Mexico. It does not aim to provide a comprehensive review of Latin America as a whole or a quantitative inventory of animal use. Instead, it uses these six countries as illustrative cases, reviewing on legal and regulatory documents, institutional sources, published and grey literature, transparency requests where available, and Te Protejo's experience in policy and regulatory discussions related to laboratory animal protection and alternative methods.

Findings: The six countries examined show heterogeneous progress. Brazil and Mexico present comparatively more developed frameworks, including more specific regulatory instruments, reporting mechanisms, and institutional structures related to laboratory animal science and alternative methods. Chile, Colombia,

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Argentina, and Peru have also made relevant advances, including animal welfare laws, ethical review mechanisms, and bans or proposals concerning cosmetic animal testing, but continue to face important gaps in implementation, oversight, transparency, and harmonized reporting. Across the six countries, the absence or partial availability of centralized animal-use data limits robust assessment of species use, procedure numbers, and the distribution of animal experimentation across sectors. Available information, including data from Brazil and Mexico and partial evidence obtained through transparency requests in Chile, suggests that rodents are among the most frequently reported species. Alternative methods, including in vitro, computational, organoid, reconstructed tissue, and other replacement-oriented approaches, are emerging through academic, regulatory, commercial, and civil society initiatives, but their uptake remains uneven and often concentrated in isolated institutions or sectors.

Conclusions: The six countries examined are at different stages of regulatory and scientific transition. Their shared challenges point to the need for stronger regulation, transparent reporting systems, clearer enforcement mechanisms, greater public access to animal-use data, and formal recognition and implementation of alternative methods. Improving regulation, transparency, and compliance in these countries would support more accountable animal research systems and create better conditions for the development and adoption of human-relevant, animal-free approaches.

Key words: *Alternative methods, Animal experimentation, Animal welfare, Bioethics, Cosmetics, Latin-America, New approach methodologies, Regulation, Toxicology, Three Rs, 3Rs*

Introduction

The use of animals in experimentation has historically been justified by the physiological, biological and genetic similarities between certain animal models and humans, enabling the extrapolation of results from animal models to human research (Henríquez, 2014). However, this justification has been increasingly questioned on both ethical and scientific grounds, including concerns regarding animal sentience, animal welfare, and the translational limitations of animal models in several areas of biomedical and toxicological research (Akhtar, 2015).

Within this context, the 3Rs principle, replacement, reduction, and refinement, has become an important ethical and scientific reference for research involving animals. Proposed by Russell and Burch in 1959, the 3Rs aim to minimize animal suffering, improve animal welfare, and promote more responsible experimental design without necessarily eliminating all animal use (Russell, 1959). Although the expression and legal recognition of concern for animals varies across cultural, institutional, and regulatory contexts, the 3Rs have

Deleted: This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the current landscape of animal experimentation in Latin America, examining regulatory frameworks and the integration of alternative methods new approach methodologies (NAMs) across six countries; Chile, Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Peru, and Mexico. Despite heterogeneous progress in regulatory development, animal welfare oversight and the incorporation of alternative methods has been made, the region continues to rely heavily on animal models for biomedical research, toxicology, agriculture, and education, with rodents constituting most laboratory use, and wildlife frequently involved in ecological and productive research. While the 3Rs principle (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) remains as one of the most mentioned ethical guiding for a responsible use of animals in research, aiming to minimize animal use and suffering without necessarily eliminating animal models, recent pioneering advances While pioneering advances, such as the ban on cosmetic animal experimentation in Colombia, México, Chile and Brazil, show a sign of regional improvement toward the gradual elimination of animal experimentation through the incorporation of validated alternative methods and the strengthening of animal welfare standards during transitional phases. Although, regulatory gaps persist due to fragmented legislation, limited oversight, and the absence of centralized data on animal use. Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees (IACUCs/CICUALES for its Spanish acronym) exist but vary widely, largely depending on institutional commitment and training. At the same time, the expansion of NAMs alternative methods including organoids, in vitro toxicity assays, and in silico or computational modeling, has begun reshaping scientific practices, supported by emerging specialized laboratories and civil society organizations. However, alternative methods NAMs adoption remains uneven and concentrated in isolated academic or commercial initiatives. Findings highlight the urgent need for standardized regulations, transparent reporting systems, increased state oversight, and stronger regional collaboration to ensure ethical, scientifically robust, and humane research practices. Overall, Latin America stands at a transitional point, where the convergence of scientific innovation, public pressure, and ethical awareness offers a unique opportunity to modernize research systems and reduce reliance on animal experimentation.¶

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been incorporated into research ethics, animal welfare guidance, and regulatory frameworks in several jurisdictions (Estévez-Moreno, 2022; Horta, 2011). For example, Directive 2010/63/EU formally incorporates the 3Rs into European Union law, while organizations such as the Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS) and the International Council for Laboratory Animal Science (ICLAS) emphasize that animals should be used for scientific purposes only when justified, when no suitable alternatives are available, and under conditions that protect their physical and psychological well-being.

In parallel, scientific and regulatory developments have contributed to the identification, validation, and acceptance of methods intended to replace animal use in specific contexts. In this commentary, the term “alternative methods” refers specifically to approaches aimed at replacing animal use, these may include, depending on the field and regulatory context, in vitro methods, reconstructed human tissues, organoids, organ-on-chip systems, computational models, omics-based approaches, and other non-animal methodologies. The availability and acceptance of such methods, however, vary considerably across scientific areas, regulatory systems, and countries.

Several international initiatives illustrate how the transition toward replacement requires not only technical development, but also validation pathways, regulatory acceptance, training, reporting standards, and institutional infrastructure. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has supported internationally harmonized test guidelines, including methods that replace animal use in specific regulatory contexts (OECD, 2020). The European Union Reference Laboratory for Alternatives to Animal Testing (EURL ECVAM) contributes to the identification, assessment, and validation of alternative methods (EURL-ECVAM, 2011). Under REACH, the European Chemicals Agency has also supported the use of non-animal information, including read-across and (Q)SAR approaches, although their regulatory application depends on adequate documentation and case-by-case assessment (ECHA, 2020; Chinen, 2020). In addition, guidelines such as ARRIVE and PREPARE have emphasized the importance of planning, reporting, transparency, reproducibility, and qualified oversight in research involving animals (Percie du Sert, 2020). Together, these examples show that progress toward replacement depends on coordinated legal, scientific, technical, and institutional conditions.

In Latin America, the regulation of animal experimentation has developed unevenly across countries. Some jurisdictions have adopted general animal protection laws, ethical review mechanisms, sector-specific regulations, or restrictions on cosmetic animal testing, while others continue to rely on fragmented legal frameworks, institutional self-regulation, or limited oversight capacity. Previous literature has identified

several persistent challenges in the region, including insufficient incorporation of animal welfare standards and the 3Rs, limited funding and infrastructure, lack of harmonized reporting systems, and uneven national capacities for implementation and enforcement (Romero-Fernandez, 2016; Rivera, 2017; Aguilera, 2022; Huete-Perez, 2025). These challenges are particularly relevant because the lack of complete, comparable, and publicly accessible animal-use data makes it difficult to assess the scale of animal experimentation, the species most frequently used, the distribution of procedures across sectors, and the effectiveness of existing oversight systems.

This evidence-informed commentary was prepared by the Research Team of Te Protejo, a civil society organization that works to advance animal-free research and disseminate bioethics progress regarding animal use, with an active presence in Chile, Argentina, Colombia, Peru, Mexico, and Brazil through staff members, volunteer networks, institutional collaborations, and participation in regulatory and policy discussions concerning the protection of animals used in laboratories and the development of alternative methods. The six countries examined were selected as illustrative cases based on the availability of accessible regulatory and institutional information, as well as Te Protejo's regional experience in these jurisdictions.

To avoid relying solely on the authors' organizational experience, this commentary draws on multiple categories of evidence, including legal and regulatory documents, institutional and governmental sources, grey literature, published scientific references, and transparency requests where available. It also identifies laboratories and initiatives working with alternative methods and considers efforts toward their development, validation, and acceptance. The scope is limited to animals used as experimental models in scientific research, experimentation, and industrial applications. It does not comprehensively address animal use in veterinary education and development, which involves distinct ethical, pedagogical, and professional considerations.

The selection and interpretation of evidence were informed by principles described by the GRADE Working Group regarding transparency in evidence assessment and consideration of limitations across different evidence sources (GRADE, 2016). Given the descriptive nature of this commentary, evidence was considered according to its methodological characteristics, institutional reliability, relevance to the research objective, and availability of verifiable information. Particular attention was given to potential limitations related to reporting inconsistencies, indirectness of available information, uneven transparency between countries, and possible institutional or publication bias. The evidence included in this commentary can be broadly categorized as legal and regulatory documents, published scientific literature, institutional grey literature, transparency data obtained through access-to-information mechanisms, and Te Protejo's organizational experience in public

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policy discussions and initiatives related to animal experimentation and alternative methods.

This commentary does not aim to provide a comprehensive review of Latin America as a whole, nor a quantitative inventory of animal use across the region. Rather, it uses six country-level examples to examine shared regulatory patterns, differences in institutional development, reporting limitations, and emerging initiatives related to alternative methods. The uneven availability and accessibility of animal-use data is therefore not only a limitation of this evidence-informed approach, but also one of the regulatory issues identified across the countries examined. Within this scope, Brazil and Mexico appear to show comparatively more developed institutional and reporting structures, while Chile, Colombia, Argentina, and Peru demonstrate relevant but uneven progress in animal welfare regulation, ethical review, transparency, and the recognition or implementation of alternative methods. By analyzing these cases together, this commentary identifies opportunities to strengthen regulation, transparency, compliance, and replacement-oriented scientific capacity in the six countries examined.

Main areas of animal experimentation in the six countries examined

Animal experimentation spans diverse fields in the six countries examined, including biomedical research, toxicology, cosmetics safety, agriculture, aquaculture, and education. These practices reflect the continued role of animal models in scientific and industrial activities, while also highlighting the relevance of regulatory frameworks capable of ensuring ethical review, transparency, animal welfare, and the development and acceptance of alternative methods aimed at replacing animal use where scientifically and legally applicable (Pérez, 2004).

Available information suggests that animals used in experimentation include laboratory animals, farm animals, aquatic species, and wild animals, depending on the research field and national regulatory context, with particular emphasis on vertebrates specially mice and rats (Navas, 2007). Laboratory animals, particularly rodents, are commonly used in biomedical and toxicological research because of their availability, relatively low maintenance costs, reproductive characteristics, and established use in experimental protocols (Franco, 2014). The former are raised under controlled conditions, altered or genetically manipulated to become models of human diseases they are partially adapted to a laboratory environment and have no contact or very little contact with exterior conditions, and mainly kept in their cages or vivarium, or the experimental room (Fagundes, 2004). However, the extent to which rats and mice are the most frequently used species across the six countries examined cannot be stated as a uniform regional fact, due to the absence of harmonized and

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Within this context, the ethical framework of the 3Rs principle (replacement, reduction and refinement), has provided an important reference point for improving animal welfare and scientific integrity in research (Russel, 1959; Estévez-Moreno, 2022). Although initially marginalized, the 3Rs principles regained prominence in the 1970s following the intensification of global discussions on animal welfare. This shift in perspective led to the establishment of the ethical framework known as the 3Rs principle, which contemplates three fundamental pillars: replacement, reduction, and refinement. Proposed by Russell and Burch in 1959, these 3Rs aim to minimize ... [1]

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publicly accessible animal-use reporting systems. In Mexico, data obtained through SENASICA and the National Transparency Platform reported 5,437,263 animals used for scientific and educational purposes between 2015 and 2021, with mice and rats representing the largest reported category (Frias-Álvarez and Ortiz-Millán, 2024). In Chile, partial information obtained through access-to-information mechanisms showed that the Institute of Public Health sold 235,510 laboratory animals in 2016, primary mice, although this reflects only one public supplier is the biggest in the country (La Tercera, 2017). Alongside international data, these sources suggest that rodents are among the most frequently reported species in the countries for which data is available, while also illustrating the limitations created by fragmented or non-public reporting systems. Farm, aquatic, and wild animals are also used in research linked to agriculture, aquaculture, ecology, biotechnology, and production systems. These animals raise additional welfare and methodological considerations, including stress from capture, marking, or disruption of their natural environment, which can trigger physiological and behavioral changes with long term impacts on their survival and reproduction (Fischer, 2019). Moreover, sample sizes required for wildlife are often larger due to population heterogeneity and changing environmental conditions (Tadich, 2020).

Universities and research centers appear to play a central role in the development of animal-based research in the countries examined. However, the visibility of animal use varies considerably between countries and institutions. In some cases, information is available through regulatory reports, institutional documents, ethics committee requirements, or public sources. In others, the lack of centralized registries, public reporting obligations, or systematic disclosure makes it difficult to assess the number of animals used, the species involved, the procedures performed, or the distribution of animal use across sectors. This uneven visibility is a central limitation for any regional assessment and is itself one of the governance issues identified in this commentary.

Biomedical research

[Animal use in biomedical research across the six countries examined.js](#) linked to the study of biological mechanisms, disease modelling, preclinical assessment, immunology, toxicology, and the development or evaluation of therapeutic and preventive interventions. Available literature suggests an overall emphasis on non-communicable diseases, including cancer, metabolic disorders, respiratory conditions, and neurological diseases, although research priorities vary across countries, institutions, and funding contexts (da Silva, 2018; Romero-Fernandez, 2016).

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Deleted: *n*, reflecting a continued reliance on animal models across these sectors, with particular emphasis on vertebrates which are mainly raised under controlled conditions and manipulated to become models of human diseases and have no contact or very little contact with exterior conditions (Navas, 2007), alongside use of farm and wild animals under distinct experimental conditions facing additional challenges such as stress from capture, marking or disruption of their natural environment (Fischer, 2019; Tadich, 2020). Although these models are still widely accepted in the development of modern medicine and production, their potential for significant advances in said areas has been debated for over a decade (Franco, 2013). While animal experimentation may be substantial and, in some contexts, increasing, limited statistical reporting restricts robust quantification of the scale and characteristics of use. In most countries, formal declaration of annual animal use or procedures is not consistently required, with some exceptions such as Mexico (SAGARPA, 20), and Brazil (AGREGAR). More than a decade ago, there were at least 584 animal species documented used in medical research across Latin America, with Brazil alone recording 326 medicinal animal species (Albuquerque, 2014). It is estimated that rats and mice are the most frequently used species (Fagundes, 2004), primarily due to their size, low cost and maintenance, and described genome, which facilitates both biological studies and gene editing or manipulation protocols (Franco, 2014). This creates uncertainty regarding species use patterns and reinforces one of the central motivations of this article, which is the need for improved transparency and stronger governance. *Avia* ... [3]

Deleted: In Latin American countries, universities and research centers lead the development of projects based on animal models. As mentioned before, despite the prevalence of animal research, the regulatory frameworks governing animal welfare and research practices remain underdeveloped, with animal facilities often lacking sufficient oversight to ensure the ethical breeding, handling, and maintenance of the species involved (Rivera, 2017). Although these models are widely accepted in the development of modern medicine and production, their potential for significant advan ... [4]

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Within this field, animals may be used to model human disease processes, evaluate biological responses, test candidate compounds, assess toxicity or safety, and support preclinical stages of biomedical research. Brazil appears as one of the most visible countries in biomedical and immunological research among the six examined, including vaccine-related research and institutional capacity for animal experimentation under CONCEA's regulatory framework. During the COVID-19 pandemic, Brazil reported several vaccine-development projects at different stages, including candidates that reached early clinical phases, illustrating the country's biomedical research capacity, although such examples should be understood as context-specific rather than as a general measure of current animal use (Faria, 2022). Argentina has also shown capacity in vaccine research and development, including the development of ARVAC (CONICET, 2023), while Mexico and Colombia have reported research activity related to infectious and neglected diseases such as dengue, Zika, tuberculosis, rabies, leishmaniasis, and Chagas disease (da Silva, 2018).

Cosmetics and self-care products

The Latin American cosmetics market is large and dominated by Brazil, with strong contributions from Mexico and Argentina (GVR, 2024). Animal testing has historically been used in the cosmetics and self care sector for safety and efficacy assessment, including tests related to eye and skin irritation, sensitization, corrosion, toxicity, and substantiation of certain product claims (Sreedhar, 2020; Divya, 2024; Silva, 2022). However, public data on the number of animals used for cosmetic testing in the six countries examined remains limited due to lack of mandatory reporting, global estimates and international literature identify rabbits, guinea pigs, rats, and mice as species historically used in this context, and estimates their number above 500,000 animals (HSI, 2019; Pritchett, 2025).

Among the six countries examined, Chile, Mexico, Colombia, and Brazil have adopted legal prohibitions or restrictions on animal testing for cosmetics and the commercialization of cosmetics tested on animals (HWA, 2023; Vilela, 2025). These developments show important regulatory progress, although their practical impact depends on implementation, enforcement, market surveillance, import controls, and the formal recognition of accepted alternative methods. In Brazil, accredited laboratories and institutional initiatives have supported the development, validation, and application of alternative methods relevant to cosmetics safety.

Agricultural production and education

Animal experimentation is used in agriculture to enhance product quality, investigate zoonotic diseases, and advance in the biotechnology field (Roca, 2017), being particularly relevant in those countries with significant

Deleted: characterized by an overall emphasis on the biological mechanisms and therapeutic targets of non-communicable diseases such as cancer, metabolic disorders and neurological conditions (da Silva, 2018), Biomedical research in Latin America is characterized by emerging scientific development, with a growing focus on elucidating biological mechanisms and developing treatment or potential cures for non-communicable diseases such as diabetes, cancer, and asthma (da Silva, 2018), while communicable disease research has remained very little in clinical trials (Anderson, 2015). The leading country on the immunological system research is Brazil. It has at least eighteen anti COVID-19 vaccine development projects in different stages of testing. Among them, at least two are on phase I of clinical trials (Faria, 2022). Argentina also has a strong potential in the research and development of human and veterinary vaccines, having developed their own COVID-19 vaccine known as ARVAC (CONICET, 2023), and a "Foot-and-mouth disease" (FMD) vaccine, which mainly affects cloven-hoofed animals, including cows, pigs or sheep, and can be deadly (León, s.f.). While neglected diseases or those caused by arboviruses like Zika or dengue, and infections like tuberculosis or rabies mainly investigated in Mexico, parasites like Leishmaniasis or chagas, and infections like tuberculosis or rabies with a strong research focus in Colombia, comprised only 1% (... [5])

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livestock and fisheries, such as Brazil, Argentina, Mexico, Chile and Colombia. In this context, research may involve cattle, pigs, poultry, fish and other farmed or aquatic species, depending on the sector and country. For example, Chile and Peru conduct research related to salmonid and avian pathogens (Gatica, 2025; Figueroa, 2022). Animals may also be used in studies involving recombinant molecules, therapeutic proteins, or gene-editing tools, including applications where animals function as biological production systems (Revista Mexicana de Ciencias Pecuarias, 2021).

These areas raise specific welfare and oversight challenges because animal use may occur outside conventional laboratory settings, including farms, aquaculture facilities, field conditions, or production-oriented research environments.

The evolution of bioethics in Latin American science

The institutionalization of bioethical oversight in Latin American science emerged later than in several jurisdictions where animal research governance became formalized earlier with a more consolidated framework such as Directive 2010/63/EU in Europe or established oversight systems in North America (Gallo, 2022). One of the main drawbacks of not having updated continental regulations is the lack of local statistics on animal welfare, therefore, the extent to which significant improvements have been incorporated is currently unknown (Resasco, 2022).

A widely cited model-based assessment estimated 79.9 million reported animal research procedures in 2015 and extrapolated a broader worldwide figure of approximately 192.1 million animals used for scientific purposes. However, these figures should be interpreted cautiously, as they rely partly on incomplete reporting and modeled assumptions, with no obtainable statistics for some regions, including South America, and significant gaps persisting in reporting from several countries (Taylor, 2020; Frías-Álvarez, 2024). In the six countries examined, the combination of limited publicly accessible animal-use data, heterogeneous regulations, limited certification systems, and cultural differences in the perception of animal sentience may increase reliance on institutional practices and on the awareness and responsibility of researchers to safeguard animal welfare (Carbone, 2021). These conditions can create uncertainty regarding whether regulations are consistently applied and whether gaps in protocol oversight, accountability, and animal housing conditions generate gray areas in practice (Mitchell, 2021).

In the absence of more specific laws, Institutional Committees for the Care and Usage of Animals (IACUCs/CICUALES for its Spanish acronym) emerged, attempting to mitigate these deficiencies by

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overseeing and regulating experiments. These committees have been adjusted in many institutions in response to the need to improve animal welfare while also strengthening institutional practices, basing their functioning in foreign models (Leland, 2019). However, their effectiveness depends on the multidisciplinary nature of their members and the implementation of comprehensive care, training, and monitoring programs (CONICYT, 2009). A critical component for the success of their programs is the establishment of a culture of care, which extends beyond regulatory compliance to emphasize the well-being of both animals and humans (Ferrara, 2022). This culture is fostered through institutional commitments, continuous training in ethics and welfare, transparent communication mechanisms, and the strengthening of oversight committees (Ameli, 2024). Animal protection groups began to emerge progressively across multiple countries in the region, driven by broader societal shift recognizing animal sentience and challenging traditional research practices (Rollin, 2011), highlighting regulatory gaps and instances of animal abuse in scientific research.

There have been notable incidents of social unrest related to animal experimentation, including protests and attacks on research facilities. In 2012, the Frente de Liberación Animal claimed responsibility for setting fire to a vehicle belonging to a researcher from Universidad de Concepción allegedly involved in animal experimentation in Chile (Bio Bio Chile, 2012). Earlier, sustained protests, particularly around primate housing, contributed to the closure of a vivarium at Pontificia Universidad Católica in 2008, which housed 88 capuchin monkeys, amid concerns over maintenance costs and ongoing questioning of animal conditions (Flores, 2016). In 2013, an activist group rescued 178 Beagles and several rabbits after allegations of malpractice and deplorable conditions at the Royal Institute of São Roque in Brazil were leaked, leading to the center's permanent closure (Arias, 2013). Evidence of animal welfare not being considered by the scientific community was also reported in a 2016 Chilean review of *in vivo* studies, in which none of the 110 articles analyzed met all ARRIVE guidelines reporting items (Galindo, 2016). And although a 2022 study from the Chilean Institute of Public Health's mouse vivarium found stress or pain indicators only in 11% of the 303 mice assessed after cage changes (Rodriguez, 2022), it should be considered that these results are representative of the analysis of only one institution, it cannot be assumed as the reality of all animal facilities in Chile. In 2023, the case of the unreported sacrifice of two community dogs at Universidad del Alba in Chile, intended for use in anatomy classes, was also documented, ultimately resulting in the dismissal of the professors involved (Fernández, 2023). Another legal analysis stated that the Chilean animal welfare system is still strongly marked by institutional self-regulation and gaps in enforcement (Ossandón, 2024).

In response to these ethical and scientific concerns, the laboratory animal science community has progressively

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developed professional organizations, scientific societies, and institutional networks aimed at strengthening standards for the care and use of animals in research. These initiatives have contributed to the dissemination of the 3Rs principles, the development of training and accreditation programs, the harmonization of animal welfare guidelines, and the promotion of alternative methods where scientifically and regulatorily feasible (Méndez, 2020). Rather than operating solely as advocacy groups, these organizations have played an important role in shaping technical guidance, supporting ethical review systems, and fostering a culture of responsibility within biomedical and experimental research. A comparative summary of representative scientific organizations and networks involved in laboratory animal welfare is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Representative organizations promoting laboratory animal science, welfare, and the 3Rs in Latin America.

Scientific and academic society	Countries involved	Contribution	Last recorded activity
Federation of South American Societies of Laboratory Animal Science (FESSACAL)	Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Uruguay, Perú and Venezuela	Development of laboratory animal science in the region (FESSACAL, 2020).	2026
Federation of Hispanic Societies and Associations of North America, Central America, and the Caribbean in Laboratory Animal Science (FESAHANCCCAL)	Mexico, Guatemala, Nicaragua, Costa Rica, Panamá, Trinidad and Tobago, Cuba, Dominican Republic, El Salvador, and	Scientific dissemination through the FESAHANCCCAL Journal, professional certification, collaboration and knowledge exchange (de Jesus, 2023)	2026

Deleted: And soThey , these protection groups started by connecting through digital technologies and enabling the formation of transnational networks, expanding their activities toward animal advocacy in diverse contexts such as advocacy-driven organizations, scientific and academic societies and institutional or regulatory initiatives, which collectively contribute to animal welfare promotion, development of alternative methods (Méndez, 2020). A comparative summary of representative organizations and networks is provided in Table 2. This multisectoral approach made it possible to advance greater visibility and challenge practices that perpetuate animal use (Méndez, 2020). Within this regional landscape, nonprofit and nongovernmental organizations have played an important role in promoting animal welfare and ethical alternatives to animal experimentation, particularly in the cosmetics sector. In Latin America, these groups have contributed to the expansion of Cruelty Free certification systems and have supported the dissemination of non-animal methodologies. ¶

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	<u>Honduras.</u>		
<u>Argentine Association of Science and Technology of Laboratory Animals (AACyTAL)</u>	<u>Argentina</u>	<u>Development and training of laboratory animal science in the region (AACyTAL, 206).</u>	<u>2026</u>
<u>Association of Technicians, Professionals and Assistants of Animal Science in Bioteriums (ATPACAL)</u>	<u>Argentina</u>	<u>Development and training of laboratory animal science in the region and promotion of good practices (Lobov, 2025).</u>	<u>2026</u>
<u>Brazilian Society of Science in Laboratory Animals (SBCAL)</u>	<u>Brazil</u>	<u>Development of laboratory animal science in the region, ethical standards, animal welfare and good research practices (SBCAL, 2023).</u>	<u>2026</u>
<u>Mexican Association of Laboratory Animal Science</u>	<u>México</u>	<u>Development of care and ethical use principles of</u>	<u>2022</u>

<u>(AMCAL)</u>		<u>laboratory animals (OIE, 2007).</u>	
<u>Chilean Association for Science and Technology of Laboratory Animals (ASOCHITAL)</u>	<u>Chile</u>	<u>Development, training and collaboration in the field of laboratory animal science and welfare (Universidad de Chile, 2024)</u>	<u>2025</u>
<u>Central American and Mexican Scientific Association on Laboratory Animals (ACCMAL)</u>	<u>Central America and Mexico</u>	<u>Development of use and welfare of laboratory animals in Central America and Mexico (Guerrero, 2014)</u>	<u>2014</u>
<u>Colombian Association for Science and Welfare of Laboratory Animals (ACCBAL)</u>	<u>Colombia</u>	<u>Development of use and welfare of laboratory animals through education, regulations, institutional strengthening and collaboration networks (ACCBAL, 2013).</u>	<u>2026</u>

The initiatives of these organizations reflect how the region has evolved from a reactive to a proactive

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approach, opening the way to adopt international standards and generate an active dialogue between science and ethics (Gemmill-Herren, 2002).

Status of animal experimentation

The current landscape of animal experimentation in six Latin American countries (Chile, Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Peru, and Mexico), is presented exploring their regulations and progress in the search for alternatives to animal use in science. In the case of Brazil, Mexico, and Argentina, their status as federal nations adds an additional layer of complexity, as regulatory norms may be applied fully or only partially across states or provinces, resulting in significant internal disparities and further challenging the standardization and comparative evaluation of animal experimentation regulations.

The identification of laboratories and initiatives working with alternative methods was informed by an independent mapping conducted by Te Protejo, developed as a living resource to identify regional capacities related to the development, validation, and application of non-animal methods (El Mostrador, 2025). Given the absence of centralized registries and standardized classifications for alternative methods laboratories in most of the countries examined, this mapping was used as a complementary source to identify illustrative examples across the six jurisdictions. Search criteria was based by the Replacing Animal Research guideline and included terms associated with alternative methods, such as in vitro models, reconstructed tissues, organoids, organ-on-chip systems, computational models, omics-based approaches, and other methodologies aimed at replacing animal use in specific scientific or regulatory contexts (Dukes, 2025). The laboratories and initiatives presented in the following country sections should therefore not be interpreted as an exhaustive count of all alternative methods capacity in each country, but rather as examples identified through an evidence-informed mapping process that may expand as additional institutions, companies, and research groups are documented.

Chile

Chile has a partial but fragmented regulatory framework governing animal use in research. The principal legal instrument is Law No. 20,380 on Animal Protection, in force since 2009, which establishes only general standards for the use of animals in scientific procedures, permits experimentation only by qualified personnel, requires adequate facilities, and seeks to minimize suffering (Chile, 2009). However, the law provides broad principles rather than detailed operational standards, delegating further guidance to the National Bioethics Committee (CBA, for its Spanish acronym), whose implementation has been delayed and whose specific

Deleted: In the context of the global bioeconomy and growing public awareness of animal welfare, the work of these organizations is very important to foster proactive approaches in the region, while international initiatives promote collaboration and technological innovation. This approach not only acknowledges public and moral concerns but also improves the quality of scientific data, reinforcing trust in research (Brown, 2018).

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guidelines remain unpublished, raising concerns regarding oversight effectiveness (Roman, 2022). Therefore, Chile has a legal basis for laboratory animal use (Ramos, 2015), but not a comprehensive and fully operational regulatory system comparable to jurisdictions with dedicated laboratory animal legislation. Its framework is supplemented by other norms that partially address specific sectors or seek to fill regulatory gaps. These include Law No. 21.646, which explicitly bans animal testing for cosmetics and encourages the development and use of alternative experimentation methods that do not involve animals (Chile, 2024), Law No. 21.020 on Responsible Pet Ownership, which addresses animal protection but largely excludes research animals (Chile, 2017), Law No. 18.892 on Fisheries and Aquaculture, which regulates experimentation involving aquatic species (Chile, 1989), and Law No. 19.473 on Hunting (Chile, 1996), which governs capture and use of wildlife for research under permit systems (SAG, 2015). In addition, the Civil Code still treats animals as property, although reforms recognizing animals as sentient beings have been proposed (Moreno-Fernández, 2023). These instruments provide a basic legal architecture; however, important weaknesses persist, including fragmented governance, limited transparency and enforcement and incomplete incorporation of animal sentience and welfare principles in the political system. The Institute of Public Health (ISP for its Spanish acronym) contributes through sanitary and pharmaceutical oversight (Acuna-Johnson, 2020), including Technical Standard N°. 57 under the Sanitary Code (CONICYT, 2013), which provides an ethical and regulatory framework relevant to biomedical research, and Resolution No. 00139, which establishes guidance for the installation and operation of vivariums under Good Laboratory Practices, incorporating animal welfare and biosecurity considerations (ISP, 2024). The Agricultural and Livestock Service (SAG) also plays a regulatory role, particularly regarding wildlife and research involving captured species through Supreme Decree N°. 5, which supports implementation of the Hunting Law and establishes welfare-related requirements for authorized use (SAG, 2015). The National Research and Development Agency (ANID) promotes compliance with bioethical principles through funding linked guidelines based on the 3Rs, applicable to funded research involving vertebrates and cephalopods (ANID, 2022). These institutions provide complementary oversight mechanisms, however, responsibilities remain fragmented across agencies.

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Deleted: This institutional dispersion represents both a structural limitation and a persistent governance challenge (Ministerio de Agricultura, 2025).

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Main experimental centers and livestock facilities

Identification of experimental centers and animal facilities in Chile is restricted by the absence of a centralized public registry and limited official reporting on animal use. This lack of transparency has been partially addressed through independent inquiries and transparency requests by civil society organizations, including No Más Vivisección and Te Protejo, which suggest that animal experimentation is concentrated primarily in public and private universities, selected public institutions and in some private activities linked to aquaculture

and livestock production (Universidad de Chile, 2024). Given these limitations, the institutions discussed are presented as illustrative examples and do not necessarily represent the activity of all the facilities involved in animal use. Among the better documented examples are the Institute of Public Health (ISP) which has and reproduces animals for the development and evaluation of biological products, pharmaceuticals, and vaccines. It has the biggest mice production for research in the country (CONICYT, 2013). The Agricultural Research Institute (INIA) conducts animal research in agricultural biotechnology and animal health (INIA, 1964), as well as the Institute of Nutrition and Food Technology (INTA) (Espinoza, 1979), and major universities such as the Universidad de Chile which houses 20 vivariums in various faculties (UCH, 2002), and Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, which doesn't declare how many vivariums they are housing at the moment but their animal research work has been associated with the biomedical, agricultural, pharmaceutical, and animal health fields (CIBEM, 2021). The lack of regulations establishing a centralized registry of experimental centers or animal farms, together with the absence of systematic information on animal use for research, limits the ability to characterize the full scope of animal experimentation in Chile.

Civil society organizations

Civil society and professional organizations have contributed to advancing animal welfare discussions, technical capacity, and promotion of alternatives to animal use in Chile. Among illustrative examples, the Chilean Association of Laboratory Animal Science and Technology (ASOCHITAL) has supported professional training, dissemination of good practices, and uptake of 3Rs principles, while also facilitating regional certification and exchange through networks associated with FESSACAL and FESAHANCCAL (Universidad de Chile, 2024). These types of organizations have contributed primarily through scientific capacity-building and standards promotion. Advocacy-oriented organizations have also played an important role, particularly in regulatory change related to cosmetics and public awareness. Te Protejo is included as an illustrative example of civil society engagement linking animal protection advocacy, policy development, and promotion of non-animal methods. Its participation in the Be Cruelty Free Chile campaign alongside Humane World for Animals, contributed to the process leading to Law No. 21,646 prohibiting animal testing for cosmetics (Te Protejo, 2014; 2025).

Alternative methods laboratories

While alternative methods still appear to represent a minority within the broader Chilean scientific landscape, the following cases illustrate emerging capacities and different modalities through which alternative methods are being developed or applied in the country. Examples include Functional Life, which applies in vitro

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Deleted: Finding laboratories that work exclusively with alternative methods remains a challenge in Chile, partly due to the absence of centralized registries and standardized classifications for these activities. The laboratories presented here should not be interpreted as an exhaustive count of all alternative methods laboratories in the country, but rather as illustrative examples identified through an independent mapping conducted by Te Protejo, using search criteria informed by the Replacing Animal Research guideline and terms associated with alternative methods (Dukes, 2025). This evidence-informed mapping is intended as a living resource and may expand as additional laboratories engaged in the development, validation and application of alternative methods are identified (Te Protejo, 2025b). While these approaches still appear to represent a minority within the broader scientific landscape, the following cases illustrate emerging capacities and different modalities through which alternative methods are being developed or applied in Chile. However, it is possible to identify at least four notable cases where the transition to alternative methods has been effective.

systems and reconstructed human skin models in food and cosmetic research (Functional Life, 2016); the Centro Científico Tecnológico de Valparaíso (CCTVal), which has developed work involving organ-on-a-chip, microfluidics, and cell culture platforms (CCTVal, 2009); Rubisco Biotechnology, which uses human cell-based models for safety and efficacy evaluation in dermocosmetic research (Rubisco, 2015); and Luyef Biotechnology, which applies cell culture, recombinant expression, and precision fermentation technologies relevant to animal-free bioindustrial applications (UCH, 2023; Luyef, 2025). Together, these initiatives suggest emerging strengths in Chile's alternative methods landscape, particularly in biomedicine and cosmetics. However, their relatively limited scale compared with broader animal-based research infrastructure underscores that uptake of alternatives remains incipient and represents an area for further development.

Argentina

Regulations and legal frameworks

Argentina lacks a comprehensive national framework specifically governing laboratory animals. Instead, oversight relies on fragmented instruments that combine general animal protection laws with sectoral and institutional regulations. While Law No. 14,346 on Animal Protection prohibits cruelty and permits vivisection only for 'scientifically demonstrable purposes' (Argentina, 1954), it fails to define criteria for scientific necessity, ethical review standards, or species-specific welfare requirements. This lack of detail leaves broad interpretive discretion and creates significant regulatory gaps in the authorization and oversight of animal experimentation. These limitations are further compounded by the absence of a unified national system for reporting animal use or monitoring compliance. Efforts to advance more specific legislation have been attempted, including the proposed Law for the Protection of Experimental Animals Used for Scientific and Educational Purposes, drafted in 2012, approved in the Chamber of Deputies in 2016, and later losing parliamentary status without enactment, illustrating both recognition of the regulatory gap and the persistence of unresolved governance limitations (AACyTAL, 2016).

This fragmented landscape is partially addressed by institutional mechanisms. For instance, the National Administration of Drugs, Food, and Medical Technology (ANMAT, for its Spanish acronym) Regulation 9236/2023 establishes good practices for animal facilities, emphasizing the 3Rs, staff training and quality management, yet its scope is primarily restricted to the pharmaceutical sector (ANMAT, 2023). Similarly, while the National Council for Scientific and Technical Research (CONICET, for its Spanish acronym), establishes guidelines for scientific research, including animal experimentation, and promotes ethical standards (FAO, 2025) and the National Vivarium System (SNB, for its Spanish acronym) supports technical

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Code of the Republic of Chile (Código Civil de la República de Chile Civil)
The Civil Code of the Republic of Chile governs the status of animals as movable property or livestock, as they can move on their own and can be owned and classified according to their usefulness. It makes no mention of animals intended for scientific research or experimentation, protecting the ownership of animals subject to compliance with relevant regulations. Its scope is limited, as it does not consider modern principles of welfare or protection, such as recognizing animals as sentient beings, an approach adopted in more advanced legislation. This creates a significant regulatory gap, especially in countries where animal experimentation still plays a substantial role in sectors such as biomedicine, pharmacology, and teaching. However, there is already a bill to modify the status of animals as sentient beings (Moreno-Fernández, 2023).
Law No. 20,380 on Animal Protection
This law has regulated animal experimentation in Chile since 2009, establishing general standards for the use of animals in scientific research, intending to ensure their well-being and minimize suffering. Regarding experimentation on live animals, it permits these practices only to qualified personnel, such as veterinarians, physicians, or scientists, and requires that establishments have adequate facilities for each species. However, it establishes only general guidelines and delegates the definition of more specific guidelines to a body competent in the associated context (Chile, 2009). The law does mention that, if noncompliance with this rule is proven, it establishes penalties ranging from fines of two to thirty monthly tax units (UTM, for its Spanish acronym), to minor to medium prison sentences with a maximum of three years.
National Bioethics Committee ... [26]

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capacity without a national animal care program requiring compliance nor formal requirements for working in animal facilities (Carbone, 2021), these initiatives do not fully resolve the challenges of uneven oversight and limited enforceability. Consequently, fragmented governance remains a central constraint within Argentina's animal research system.

Main experimental centers and livestock facilities

Several experimental centers and animal production facilities have incorporated approaches that combine animal models with alternative methodologies to reduce the use of animals in research. In Argentina, the National System of Animal Facilities (Sistema Nacional de Bioterios, SNB), an initiative of the Secretariat of Innovation, Science and Technology (SICYT), seeks to optimize the condition, operation, and service provision of animal facilities that house laboratory animals for breeding, experimentation, biological testing, or teaching. According to the official SNB registry, 97 animal facilities are currently registered, providing an institutional framework to identify and document vivariums (SICYT, n.d.). The National Institute of Agricultural Technology (INTA) in Argentina does not directly regulate animal experimentation, but plays an important role by using animal models in studies of zoonoses, livestock production, and agricultural biotechnology, while integrating in vitro and in silico tools to assess the toxicity of agricultural and biotechnological products. It also provides training to producers and technicians on proper animal handling, contributing to improved animal welfare and a reduction in experimental use (INTA, 2021). In a complementary way, the Central Vivarium of Garrahan Hospital is recognized for its high ethical standards and adoption of alternative methods, while the Research Center of the Faculty of Pharmacy and Biochemistry at Universidad de Buenos Aires is developing in silico systems to predict chemical reactions and health effects without the use of animals (Meiorin, 2024).

Civil society organizations

Civil society organizations in Argentina play a key role in promoting animal welfare, alternative methodologies, and ethical standards in research. The Argentinian Animal Welfare Association (ASARBA), founded in 2008 under the Society of Veterinary Medicine in Buenos Aires, focuses on promoting animal welfare through education, outreach, and research, while fostering collaboration with national and international organizations and serving as an advisory body on animal welfare issues (ASARBA, 2024). The Alternative Methods Argentinian Network (RAMA) is a scientific initiative aimed at advancing the implementation of alternative methodologies aligned with the 3Rs principle, promoting regulatory acceptance of OECD-validated methods through collaboration with agencies such as ANMAT and SENASA, and

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Deleted: Law No. 14,346 on Animal Protection[¶] Prohibits animal abuse, penalizing acts of cruelty such as torture, unnecessary death, and lack of basic care with penalties ranging from 15 days to 1 year in prison. The statement regarding animal experimentation for scientific, as vivisection is allowed for "scientifically demonstrable purposes and in places or by persons duly authorized", with no clear definition of what constitutes a scientifically demonstrable purpose (Argentina, 1954). As a result, by failing to establish strict criterion for authorizing experimentation, the law might justify a wide range of experiments. [¶] Regulatory institutions[¶] National Administration of Drugs, Food, and Medical (... [27])

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organizing key events like the 2017 national workshop and the 2018 Latin American Congress of Alternative Methods (COLAMA), which strengthened interdisciplinary dialogue (Rivero, 2019). In parallel, the Argentine Association for Laboratory Animal Science and Technology (AACyTAL) is a non-profit organization dedicated to improving laboratory animal science through ethical and standardized practices, providing extensive training and education, and fostering international collaboration, including participation in ICLAS and its role as a founding member of FESSACAL (AACyTAL, 1981).

Alternative methods laboratories

Alternative methods laboratories in Argentina are focused on developing and validating non-animal approaches for safety and efficacy testing across multiple industries. The Alternative Methods Laboratory (LMA), part of the EBAL consortium and founded in 2016, is the first specialized laboratory in the country dedicated entirely to alternative methodologies to animal experimentation. It is fully equipped to generate knowledge, validate, apply, and transfer non-animal methods, with applications in preclinical research and industries such as cosmetics, agrochemicals, and household cleaning products (LMA, 2022). In addition, CLAIM, a pioneering Contract Research Organization (CRO), evaluates the safety and efficacy of a wide range of products including cosmetics, personal care items, veterinary supplies, dietary supplements, and pharmaceuticals through human clinical trials. Its work includes assessments of dermal and ocular irritation, sensitization, gynecological safety, and validation of product claims such as hypoallergenic or non-comedogenic properties, as well as efficacy studies related to skin health, hydration, antioxidant effects, and aging (CLAIM, 1999).

Brazil

Regulations and legal frameworks

Brazil has developed a legal and regulatory framework for animal use in science that combines ethical oversight with increasing restrictions on animal testing. Law No. 11,794 (Arouca Law) establishes the main standards for the use of animals in scientific and educational research, requiring ethical review of research projects and promoting the reduction of animal suffering, as well as encouraging the use of alternative methods whenever possible (Dittrich, 2019). Complementarily, Decree 6,899/2009 regulates the implementation of this law by defining procedures for the creation and functioning of ethics committees, CEUAs, as well as clarifying the responsibilities of researchers and institutions using animals (Meloni, 2024). Broader legal instruments such as Law 9,605/1998 (Environmental Crimes Law) also address animal protection by penalizing

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Subjected to the Society of Veterinary Medicine based in Buenos Aires, the Argentinian Animal Welfare Association (ASARBA, for its Spanish acronym), was founded on November 26, 2008. Its main objective is to promote animal welfare through outreach, research, and education, both in public and private settings. Its goals include raising awareness about the proper treatment of animals, by promoting research related to animal welfare, disseminating scientific knowledge, in universities and graduate programs. It also seeks to establish links with national and international organizations that share its objectives, serving as a consultative and advisory body on issues related to animal welfare (ASARBA, 2024). ¶
Alternative Methods Argentinian Network (Red Argentina de Métodos Alternativos) ¶
The Alternative Methods Argentinian Network (RAMA, for its Spanish acronym), has emerged as a coordinated initiative of researchers committed to advancing the implementation of non-animal methodologies in Argentina, in response to the growing global shift toward the 3Rs paradigm. The network was formed after a series of meetings among scientists seeking to promote alternative testing strategies and to encourage national regulators, such as ANMAT and SENASA to recognize validated OECD methods for toxicological assessment. RAMA organized the first national Workshop on Alternative Methods to the Use of Animals in Experimentation in 2017, followed by the hosting of the Latin American Congress of Alternative Methods (COLAMA for its Spanish acronym) in 2018, events that catalyzed dialogue among academia, industry, and regulatory bodies (Rivero, 2019). ¶
Argentine Association for Laboratory Animal Science (... [30])

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Deleted: Alternative Methods Laboratory (Laboratorio de Métodos Alternativos) ¶

Deleted: Part of the EBAL consortium, founded in 2016, the Alternative Methods Laboratory (LMA, for its Spanish acronym) is the first laboratory in Argentina specializing in NAMs as an alternative to animal experimentation. Fully equipped, it is committed to generating knowledge, validating, applying, training, and transferring method (... [32])

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mistreatment and cruelty, including in research contexts (Brazil, 2009). In addition, Article 82 of the Brazilian Civil Code historically classified animals as property, although this interpretation has been increasingly challenged in favor of recognizing animals as sentient beings (Regis, 2017). More recently, Brazil has advanced in restricting animal testing in specific sectors through Law 3062/22, approved in 2025, which bans the use of vertebrate animals for testing cosmetic products, personal care items, and perfumes, as well as the commercialization of products tested on animals, with limited exceptions aligned with international regulations. This milestone was driven by collaborative advocacy efforts from organizations such as Humane World for Animals, Fórum Animal, and Te Protejo, supported by over 1.6 million signatures (Vilela, 2025).

The National Council for the Control of Animal Experimentation (CONCEA, for its Portuguese acronym) publishes regulations and guidelines that complement the Arouca Law and encourages animal welfare ethics in research (CONCEA, 2021).

Main experimental centers and livestock facilities

The Butantan Institute is internationally recognized for its research and production of vaccines, antivenoms, and treatments for tropical diseases, relying on animal models under strict ethical and scientific regulations (Butantan Institute, 1901). Similarly, the Oswaldo Cruz Foundation (Fiocruz) is a leading biomedical research institution in Brazil, specialized in vaccine development, epidemiological studies, and infectious disease research, and it incorporates animal welfare principles within its experimental practices (Fiocruz, 1900). At the national level, CONCEA's most recent report on animal use in teaching and research, based on annual reports submitted by accredited institutions, recorded 11,390,421 animals used in Brazil between 2019 and 2023, of which 10,927,919 were reported for research and 462,502 for teaching activities. The report also indicates that the most frequently used animal groups in research were birds, fish, and rodents, representing 33.7%, 25.9%, and 17.7% of reported use, respectively, while teaching activities were mainly associated with birds, large ruminants, and fish. These findings suggest that animal use in Brazil is not limited to biomedical research, but also reflects the importance of agricultural, veterinary, toxicological, and production-related fields within the national research system (CONCEA, 2024).

Civil society organizations

Humane World for Animals has played an active role in Brazil's campaign to ban cosmetic animal testing, supporting long-term advocacy efforts that culminated in the 2025 advancement of the federal ban by the Brazilian Chamber of Deputies (HWA, 2025). In parallel, the Fórum Nacional de Proteção e Defesa Animal

Deleted: Law No. 11,794 Arouca

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Decree 6.899/2009
This decree regulates the implementation of Law 11.794/2008, establishing procedures for the creation and operation of ethical committees in animal experimentation. It also defines the responsibilities of researchers and institutions that use animals in their studies (Meloni, 2024).
Law 9.605/1998 (Environmental Crimes Law)
Although not exclusively focused on animal welfare, this law includes provisions prohibiting mistreatment and animal cruelty. It establishes penalties for those who cause suffering to animals, including those used in research (Brazil, 2009).

Brazilian Civil Code (Article 82)
This article classifies domestic animals as livestock, objects in legal terms. However, this has been the subject of debate, and modifications have been endorsed to recognize animals as sentient beings (Regis, 2017).
Law 3062/22 that bans the use of vertebrate animals in testing for cosmetic products, personal care items, and perfumes

On July 9, 2025 the Bill 3062/22 was approved. This federal law prohibits the use of vertebrate animals in testing for cosmetic products, personal care items, and perfumes, and bans the sale of products or ingredients tested on animals, except in specific cases required by international regulations. The law is the result of a collective effort, led by organizations such as Humane World for Animals, Forum Animal and Te Protejo, and supported by over 1.6 million people who signed the petition (Vilela, 2025).

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Fundação Oswaldo Cruz (Fiocruz)
The Oswaldo Cruz Foundation is the leading research center in Brazil specialized in vaccine development, epidemiological studies, and infectious diseases, advoc...

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(Fórum Animal) is a Brazilian non-profit organization dedicated to animal protection and the abolition of cruelty and abusive practices. It promotes awareness and policy change through legal advocacy, education, and campaigns, and also develops the “Ciência Sem Jaulas” platform, which provides accessible information on animal experimentation, regulatory frameworks, bioethics, and alternative methods that can replace animal use in science (Fórum Animal, 1998).

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Alternative methods laboratories

Alternative methods laboratories in Brazil are increasingly focused on replacing animal experimentation through advanced *in vitro*, *in silico*, and human-relevant technologies across biomedical, cosmetic, and toxicological research. The Brazilian National Network of Alternative Methods (RENAMA) promotes the research, development, and validation of alternative methodologies to animal use, fostering the adoption of modern and ethical technologies across multiple scientific fields (RENAMA, 2017). The Brazilian Biosciences National Laboratory (LNBio) is a pioneer in the country in the use of organoids and computational (*in silico*) approaches for advanced biomedical research, contributing to the development of non-animal alternatives (LNBio, 2021). In parallel, The Laboratory for the Development and Validation of Alternative Methods (LaMaBio) focuses on the creation and validation of *in vitro* systems for toxicity assessment, including 2D and 3D cell cultures, spheroid formation, and molecular analyses, while also providing training in alternative methodologies (LaMaBio, 2004). Complementing these efforts, EthiCell Solutions drives the transition toward animal-free science by offering digital tools, human cell-based systems, and animal-free reagents to support toxicology, preclinical testing, and cell therapy research (EthiCell, 2025). Similarly, Kosmoscience specializes in *in vitro* and clinical testing for cosmetic and dermatopharmaceutical products, using advanced molecular and cellular techniques to assess safety and efficacy (Kosmoscience, 2003). Episkin, part of L’Oréal Research and Innovation, develops reconstructed human tissue models such as SkinEthic RHE and HCE for applications in irritation, corrosion, and sensitization testing, providing human-relevant alternatives widely used in the cosmetic industry (Episkin, 1994). Finally, the National Institute of Metrology, Quality and Technology (INMETRO) supports alternative methodologies through its RENAMA program by validating testing methods and ensuring quality and safety standards in sectors such as cosmetics and agrochemicals, contributing to the regulatory acceptance of non-animal approaches (INMETRO, 1973). Within this ecosystem, the Brazilian Center for the Validation of Alternative Methods (BraCVAM), located at the Oswaldo Cruz Foundation (Fiocruz), plays a central role in strengthening the development, validation, and regulatory pathway of alternative methods in Brazil. BraCVAM acts as a focal point for the validation process, supports the development and coordination of validation studies, evaluates protocols and results, promotes scientific

Deleted: This organization has been active in Brazil in the campaign to ban cosmetic animal experimentation. After years of advocacy, they celebrated the Brazilian Chamber of Deputies vote in July 2025 advancing the federal ban (HWA, 2025).[¶]

Fórum Nacional de Proteção e Defesa Animal [¶]
The National Forum for Animal Protection and Defense (Fórum Animal for its simplification) is a non-profit, multidisciplinary organization dedicated to animal protection and defense across Brazil. Their mission is to raise awareness and change society to abolish cruelty, suffering, and abusive practices toward animals. The organization also curates *Ciência Sem Jaulas* (Science without cages), an extensive knowledge platform which provides accessible resources on animal experimentation, regulatory frameworks and documented alternatives that can replace harmful animal use. Through legal advocacy, public-policy engagement, education, and campaigns, Fórum Animal works to ensure respect for the sentience and wellbeing of all animals, intervening in issues from animal exploitation and laboratory testing to trafficking and environmental disasters (Fórum animal, 1998). [¶]

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dissemination and international cooperation, and may issue recommendations to CONCEA, which is responsible for the regulatory adoption of validated methods in Brazil (BraCVAM, n.d.; Presgrave et al., 2016).

Colombia

Regulations and legal frameworks

Colombia has progressively developed a regulatory framework for animal protection and welfare in research and society, integrating ethical principles and international standards. Law 1774 of 2016 recognizes animals as sentient beings and establishes a legal framework based on principles of respect, solidarity, compassion, and justice, while incorporating the “Five Freedoms” of the World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH) as a basis for assessing animal welfare (Colombia, 2016). Similarly, Law 1955 of 2019, within the 2018–2022 National Development Plan, reinforces national policy for the protection and welfare of domestic and wild animals, also integrating the Five Freedoms and assigning leadership in its implementation to the Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development (Colombia, 2019). In addition, Law 84 of 1989 provides early regulatory guidelines for the use of live animals in experimentation and research, aiming to ensure humane treatment and welfare standards (Colombia, 1989). More recently, Law 2047 of 2021 prohibits the use of animals in cosmetic testing; however, its implementation has faced delays due to the need for specific regulations, despite its formal entry into force in 2024, raising concerns regarding enforcement (Infobae, 2024). At the policy level, Draft Agreement 128 of 2010 sought to establish animal protection guidelines and educational programs in Bogotá but was ultimately not approved and therefore did not become binding legislation (Consejo de Bogotá, 2010).

Regulatory institutions in Colombia play an important role in overseeing scientific practices and promoting ethical standards in animal use. The National Institute for Food and Drug Surveillance (INVIMA) is responsible for regulating animal studies within the context of pharmaceuticals and food safety, and it actively promotes the incorporation of alternative methods in research processes (INVIMA, 2023). In the field of biomedical research, the National Institute of Health (Instituto Nacional de Salud) is a leading institution focused on infectious diseases and public health, conducting studies under protocols that prioritize animal welfare in experimental settings (Patiño, 2017). In addition, the International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) is dedicated to sustainable agricultural development, using ethical experimental models and certified animal facilities to evaluate environmental impacts and improve agricultural productivity in tropical regions (CIAT, 2013).

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A pioneer in Brazil in alternative methods to animal experimentation, such as the use of organoids and in silico techniques, focusing on advanced biomedical research (LNBio, 2021).¶
Rede Nacional de Métodos Alternativos ao Uso de Animais¶
The Brazilian National Network of Alternative Methods (RENAMA, for its Portuguese acronym) promotes the research, development, and validation of alternative methods to the use of animals in Brazil, promoting modern and ethical technologies in various scientific fields (RENAMA, 2017).¶
Laboratório de Desenvolvimento e Validação de Métodos Alternativos ¶
The Laboratory for the Development and Validation of Alternative Methods (LaMaBio, for its Portuguese acronym) is dedicated to the validation, development and application of innovative in vitro methodologies for the evaluation of toxicity, focusing on assays such as antifungal efficacy, proteomic and genomic analysis for microbiology, and the use of 2D and 3D cell cultures. The laboratory also specializes in the formation of spheroids from various cell lines and provides teaching and training in alternative methodologies for academic and business environments (LaMaBio, 2004).¶
EthiCell Solutions¶
EthiCell Solutions leads the transition to vegan science and innovative digital platforms, facilitating access to animal-free reagents and alternative methods for laboratories and biomedical industries. The company specializes in process automation and the adaptation of protocols to develop alternative methods. It also provides guidance on safety and efficacy for toxicology, preclinical experimentation, and cell therapies. EthiCell Solutions offers products like HumanE Sumus, which identifies animal-free reagents and human cell lines, and ethiCalc, which precisely calculates the required volumes of culture media and solutions for each stage of the FBS elimination process. Furthermore, the company supplies animal-free culture media and reagents to sup[... [34]

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Civil society organizations

The Colombian Association for the Science and Welfare of Laboratory Animals (ACCBAL), for its Spanish acronym) is a non-profit organization dedicated to promoting the ethical use and welfare of animals employed in scientific research in Colombia. Their work focuses on education, the development of regulations, and the fostering of collaborative networks among professionals, ensuring responsible practices aligned with the highest ethical standards (ACCBAL, 2013).

Alternative methods laboratories

Alternative methods laboratories in Colombia are advancing the development of alternative methods for biomedical, toxicological, and industrial applications. Novum Science is focused on bioink development and 3D bioprinting of tissues for the biomedical and dermocosmetic industries, including work on cell incorporation into biostructures, viability assessments, and tissue engineering applications, as well as consulting services in bioprinting and artificial tissue development (Novum Science, 2023). In parallel, the In Vitro Toxicity Unit at Universidad CES specializes in toxicological evaluation of raw materials, ingredients, products, and environmental contaminants across multiple sectors such as pharmaceuticals, food, cosmetics, medical devices, agriculture, and mining. Its services include cytotoxicity, genotoxicity, dermal and ocular irritation testing, as well as safety evaluation and prototyping of products and cosmetic ingredients (UTI, 2014).

Peru

Regulations and legal frameworks

Peru has included animal welfare and a general prohibition of the use of animals in scientific research within its general animal protection legislation, although the available public information suggests that its institutional implementation remains limited and difficult to verify. Law No. 30,407 establishes the legal basis for animal welfare, providing that experimentation, research, and teaching involving animals may only take place in higher education institutions or specialized public or private centers with animal welfare ethics committees, and only when the expected results cannot be obtained through methods that do not involve animals. The law also provides for the creation of a National Ethics Committee for Animal Welfare, composed of six members and tasked with evaluating the criteria used by institutional ethics committees to establish animal welfare parameters. However, publicly available information identified in this review does not allow confirmation that this committee has been effectively constituted, nor that it has produced publicly accessible guidelines, reports,

Deleted: The National Institute for Food and Drugs Surveillance regulates animal studies, promoting the use of alternative methods in research (INVIMA, 2023).
Main experimental centers and livestock facilities
Instituto Nacional de Salud
The National Institute of Health is one of the leading entities in medical research and the regulation of the Colombian healthcare industry. Researching issues related to infectious diseases and public health, employing protocols that prioritize animal welfare in its studies (Patiño, 2017).
Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical
The International Center for Tropical Agriculture focuses on sustainable agricultural development. Ethical models and certified animal farms are employed to assess environmental impact and improve agricultural production in the tropical region (CIAT, 2013).

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Deleted: Novum Science focuses on the development of bioinks and 3D bioprinting of tissues for the biomedical and dermocosmetic industries. Their work includes cell incorporation and culture in biostructures, viability tests, and cellular cultures. Novum Science is also dedicated to advancing tissue and artificial organ growth, offering consulting in tissue engineering and bioprinting (Novum science, 2023).

In vitro Toxicity unit, Universidad CES
This laboratory specializes in toxicological evaluations of raw materials, ingredients, products, and environmental contaminants for various sectors, including pharmaceuticals, food, biomaterials, medical devices, cosmetics, personal care products, mining, and agriculture. Their testing includes cytotoxicity, genotoxicity, ocular and dermal irritation, safety testing, prototyping, and testing of cosmetic ingredients and products (UTI, 2014).

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Deleted: oped a regulatory framework aimed at strengthening animal protection and limiting the use of animals in scientific research

decisions, or other visible outputs (Law No. 30,407). The framework may also intersect with the regulatory functions of the National Directorate of Medicines, Medical Devices and Drugs (DIGEMID) particularly in areas related to medicines, health products, and safety assessment, although available public information does not indicate that DIGEMID operates as a dedicated authority for the oversight of animal experimentation. In addition, Bill 07688/2023-CR is currently under legislative review and proposes to ban the use, commercialization, and importation of cosmetic products tested on animals, reflecting ongoing efforts to strengthen animal protection policies in the country (Te Protejo, 2025).

Regulatory institutions in Peru oversee both pharmaceutical control and public and environmental health, with mostly indirect relevance to animal welfare and research practices. The General Directorate of Medicines, Supplies and Drugs (DIGEMID) supervises procedures related to medicines and health products, which may indirectly relate to the evaluation of safety data and the potential use of alternative methods, but its publicly available institutional role should not be interpreted as a comprehensive animal-experimentation oversight mechanism (DIGEMID, 2023). In parallel, the General Directorate of Environmental Health (DIGESA) is not directly responsible for regulating animal experimentation, but plays a key role in environmental health, food safety, and zoonosis control. Through its surveillance functions, DIGESA contributes to animal health regulation, particularly in preventing and controlling diseases that can be transmitted from animals to humans (DIGESA, 2010).

Main experimental centers and livestock facilities

Main experimental centers and livestock facilities in Peru contribute to biomedical research, agricultural development, and aquaculture while incorporating animal welfare standards and, in some cases, ethical experimental models. The National Institute of Health (Instituto Nacional de Salud) leads biomedical and public health research, working with certified animal facilities that ensure high welfare standards in scientific studies. Similarly, the Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos maintains certified animal facilities for biomedical and agricultural research, promoting ethical practices in animal use (UNMSM, 2021). In the field of aquatic sciences, Native Fish Research Centers for Sustainable Aquaculture focus on species conservation and sustainable aquaculture, using ethical models to study the biology and development of native fish species (SNP, 2022).

Civil society organizations

Asociación para el rescate y bienestar de los animales (ARBA, for its Spanish acronym) aims to raise

Deleted: restricting the use of animals in scientific experimentation to cases where no validated alternative methods are available, and incorporating oversight mechanisms such as the National Ethics Committee for Animal Welfare, which evaluates compliance with welfare criteria and promotes a precautionary approach to animal sentience.

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awareness and promote societal change to improve the quality of life for animals in Peru. Through community engagement, they create change agents who are critical in ending the abuse suffered by millions of animals. The organization encourages direct action, such as signing petitions, making donations, and supporting legislative activism. ARBA is committed to creating a more just world for animals and advocating for their protection through various campaigns and initiatives, including hosting the 2nd Latin American Animal Law Congress in 2024 (ARBA, 2024). It currently supports alongside Te Protejo, [the previously mentioned bill](#) to ban animal testing for cosmetics in Peru.

Alternative methods laboratories

The Technological Institute of Production (ITP) has implemented advanced technology, reducing the use of animals in laboratory tests for scientific research within their facilities to zero. The ITP operates through a network of Productive Innovation and Technology Transfer Centers (CITE), which cover diverse production chains: agribusiness, fishing and aquaculture, forestry and wood, apparel (leather, footwear, textiles and clothing), energy, materials and mining, marketing and logistics, and creative industries (ITP, 2025).

Mexico

Regulations and legal frameworks

Mexico has established a regulatory framework for the ethical use and protection of animals in research, combining mandatory standards with evolving legislation. The Mexican Official Standard NOM-062-ZOO-1999 sets the technical requirements for the production, care, and use of laboratory animals, requiring institutions to implement internal committees to ensure compliance with ethical and welfare standards, with oversight and reporting obligations linked to SENASICA to standardize implementation at the federal level (Secretaría de Agricultura, 1999). In addition, the Regulations of the Animal Protection Law define the procedures and responsibilities of authorities in enforcing animal welfare legislation, including supervision of animal experimentation and the promotion of education on humane treatment. More recently, the reform of the General Health Law prohibits the use of animals in cosmetic testing and encourages the development of alternative methods to ensure product safety without animal suffering, although its full implementation depends on the publication of a specific NOM to make it operational (Te Protejo, 2024).

Regulatory institutions in Mexico oversee animal health, public health safety, and ethical standards in scientific research through specialized governmental bodies. The National Service for Agri-Food Health, Safety, and

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Deleted: Establishes technical specifications for the production, care, and use of laboratory animals. This standard is mandatory, requiring institutions to develop internal committees for the care and use of animals that ensure the fulfillment of ethical and welfare practices. Although there may be some diversity in its implementation and oversight at the state level, this fundamental regulation is implemented at the federal level to ensure standardization across all entities in the country (Secretaría de Agricultura, 1999). This regulation demands reporting of animal use to the institutions directly so SENASICA. [¶] Regulations of the Animal Protection Law [¶] Details the procedures and responsibilities of authorities in implementing the law, including supervising animal experiments and promoting education on dignified treatment. [¶] Reform of the General Health Law [¶] It prohibits the use of animals for cosmetics testing, promoting the development and implementation of alternative methods to ensure product safety without resorting to animal suffering. However, to become operational, a specific NOM needs to be published (Frias-Álvarez, 2024). [¶]

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Quality (SENASICA) is responsible for protecting animal and plant health and ensuring food safety, and it carries out activities that may involve animal experimentation, particularly in animal health. Within SENASICA, the National Center for Animal Health Diagnostic Services (CENASA) operates specialized laboratories in fields such as bacteriology, virology, serology, and pathology, supporting quality control of biological products and conducting bioassays (Schaller, 2024). In parallel, the Federal Commission for the Protection against Sanitary Risks (COFEPRIS) regulates cosmetics, medical devices, and clinical research, ensuring compliance with safety, quality, and ethical standards by evaluating protocols and authorizing studies under a defined regulatory framework (COFEPRIS, 2023). Additionally, the National Bioethics Commission (CONBIOÉTICA) is a decentralized body of the Ministry of Health with technical autonomy, responsible for developing bioethics policy and promoting knowledge dissemination, including topics related to animal welfare (México, 2017).

Main experimental centers and livestock facilities

A 2024 study based on 330 transparency requests submitted through Mexico's National Transparency Platform to public research centres, schools, hospitals, national institutes, technical colleges, and public universities provides one of the few available estimates of animal use for scientific and educational purposes in the country. According to the data obtained, Mexican public institutions reported the use of 2,112,786 animals between 2015 and October 2021. Mammals were the most frequently used group, with 1,220,894 animals, followed by fish, with 513,722; reptiles, with 130,944; birds, with 118,784; insects and arachnids, with 102,967; amphibians, with 11,501; crustaceans, with 10,053; mollusks, with 1,432; other invertebrates, with 1,244; and animals reported as unknown, with 1,245. The study also found that only 54% of the institutions reporting animal use had functional ethics committees, and emphasized that the absence of comprehensive public records, mandatory registration of committees, certification processes for animal facilities, and external oversight mechanisms makes the available figures likely incomplete and points to the need to update Mexican regulations on the use, protection, and care of laboratory animals (Frias-Álvarez and Ortiz-Millán, 2024). Within this context, main experimental centers and livestock facilities in Mexico play a central role in biomedical, clinical, and agricultural research, while incorporating ethical and welfare standards in animal use. The Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México (UNAM) is a leading institution in biomedical research and toxicology, maintaining specialized animal facilities for studies in human and animal health under established ethical and scientific guidelines (UNAM, 2022). Similarly, the Instituto Nacional de Ciencias Médicas y Nutrición Salvador Zubirán is a key center for advanced biomedical research, using animal models to investigate chronic diseases, develop therapies, and evaluate pharmaceuticals under strict animal welfare

Deleted: National Service for Agri-Food Health, Safety, and Quality (Servicio Nacional de Sanidad, Inocuidad y Calidad Agroalimentaria)¶

Deleted: Mexico's National Service for Agri-Food Health, Safety, and Quality (SENASICA, for its Spanish acronym) is the entity responsible for protecting animal and plant health and food safety in the country. Among its functions, SENASICA performs activities that may involve animal experimentation, especially in animal health. One of SENASICA's main facilities is the National Center for Animal Health Diagnostic Services (CENASA), which has specialized laboratories in bacteriology, virology, serology, and pathology. These laboratories conduct quality control tests for biological products and have modern bioassay units (Schaller, 2024).¶

Comisión Federal para la Protección contra Riesgos Sanitarios¶

The Federal Commission for the Protection against Sanitary Risks (COFEPRIS, for its Spanish acronym) oversees the regulatory control of cosmetics, medical devices, and clinical research, ensuring compliance with safety and quality standards. Its mandate includes evaluating study protocols, authorizing research, and monitoring adherence to ethical and sanitary regulations. Its regulatory framework establishes the conditions under which studies must demonstrate scientific validity and public-health protection (COFEPRIS, 2023).¶

Comisión Nacional de Bioética¶

The National Bioethics Commission (CONBIOÉTICA, for its Spanish acronym) is a decentralized body of the Ministry of Health with technical and operational autonomy. Its functions include policy formulation and the dissemination of knowledge in bioethics, including animal welfare (México, 2017).¶

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standards (Orozco, 2003). In the agricultural sector, the National Institute for Forestry, Agricultural, and Livestock Research (INIFAP) focuses on improving animal health, productivity, and sustainable biotechnological applications in livestock and agricultural systems through the use of animal models (FAO, 2025b).

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Alternative methods laboratories

Alternative methods laboratories in Mexico are increasingly focused on replacing or reducing animal use through advanced in vitro systems, 3D tissue models, and computational approaches for safety and toxicological assessment. The Laboratorio de Investigación Alternativa (LIALT) specializes in toxicological evaluations of chemicals, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and household products using 3D human cell-based tissues, conducting assays such as dermal, ocular, vaginal irritation, sensitization, corrosion, and cytotoxicity testing (LIALT, 2017). ILAB In Vitro Toxicology Mexico applies advanced reconstructed human tissue models to assess dermal and ocular irritation, sensitization, phototoxicity, photosensitization, and acute toxicity, contributing to non-animal safety evaluation methods (ILAB, 2019). The Total Analytical Quality Control Laboratory (CCAT) provides in vitro 3D testing for cosmetic and raw material safety, including irritation, sensitization, corrosivity, and microbiological and physicochemical analyses for product evaluation (CCAT, 2005). In parallel, the Center for Research and Advanced Studies (CINVESTAV) develops and applies computational models in pharmacology, supporting the advancement of ethical and non-animal-based scientific research methodologies (CINVESTAV, 2023).

Deleted: The Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México (UNAM, for its Spanish acronym) is a benchmark in biomedical research and toxicology, with specialized animal facilities for human and animal health studies, promoting ethical and scientific standards in animal experimentation (UNAM, 2022).

Instituto Nacional de Ciencias Médicas y Nutrición Salvador Zubirán

Instituto Nacional de Ciencias Médicas y Nutrición Salvador Zubirán leads in advanced biomedical research; it uses animal models to study chronic diseases, develop therapies, and evaluate drugs under strict animal welfare standards (Orozco, 2003).

National Institute for Forestry, Agricultural, and Livestock Research (Instituto Nacional de Investigaciones Forestales, Agrícolas y Pecuarias)

The National Institute for Forestry, Agricultural, and Livestock Research (INIFAP, for its Spanish acronym) is fundamental for agricultural research; it uses animal models to improve animal health, increase productivity, and develop sustainable biotechnologies in the agricultural and livestock sectors (FAO, 2025b).

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Comparative overview

Table 2. Comparative overview of animal-use governance, public data availability, and alternative methods capacity in the six countries examined.

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Country	Regulatory status	Public data and reporting	Alternative methods capacity
Brazil	Most structured framework: Arouca Law, CEUAs, CONCEA, and	Centralized reporting: CONCEA 11,390,421	Most developed ecosystem: RENAMA, BraCVAM, LNBio.

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	<u>cosmetic testing restrictions.</u>	<u>animals reported in teaching and research between 2019–2023.</u>	<u>LaMaBio, INMETRO, Episkin, Kosmoscience, EthiCell.</u>
<u>Mexico</u>	<u>Technical regulation through NOM-062, with SENASICA, COFEPRIS, and CONBIOÉTICA. Cosmetic testing reform still requires operational rules.</u>	<u>Transparency-based estimate: 2,112,786 animals reported by public institutions between 2015–2021; reporting remains incomplete.</u>	<u>Strong and growing: LIALT, ILAB, CCAT, CINVESTAV, 3D tissues, in vitro toxicology, and computational models.</u>
<u>Colombia</u>	<u>Relevant legal recognition of animal sentience and welfare principles; cosmetic testing ban with implementation challenges.</u>	<u>No centralized public animal-use reporting system identified.</u>	<u>Emerging: Novum Science and Universidad CES In Vitro Toxicity Unit.</u>
<u>Chile</u>	<u>Fragmented framework: Law 20.380, Law 21.646, CBA mandate, and sectoral rules.</u>	<u>No centralized registry or national animal-use statistics; information remains partial and only available through</u>	<u>Emerging but limited: Functional Life, CCTVal, Rubisco Biotechnology, Luyef Biotechnology.</u>

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		transparency requests.	
Argentina	Fragmented framework; Law 14.346, ANMAT rules, CONICET structures, and SNB registry.	No unified animal-use reporting; SNB identifies 97 registered animal vivariums.	Limited but emerging: RAMA, LMA, CLAIM, and in silico initiatives
Peru	General animal protection law includes research provisions, but implementation is difficult to verify.	No centralized animal-use statistics or visible national reporting system identified.	Limited and early-stage; few identifiable initiatives.

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Note. This table summarizes illustrative examples and does not provide an exhaustive inventory of institutions, laboratories, or animal-use data.

Across the six Latin American countries analyzed, the landscape of animal experimentation and alternative methods reflects a clear transition phase, where traditional animal-based research infrastructures coexist with expanding adoption of alternative methods.

Conclusions

Across the six Latin American countries analyzed, regulation of animal use in science shows a common shift toward recognizing animal welfare ethical review, and, to varying degrees, the incorporation of the 3Rs principle. However, this development has not followed a uniform path, but with clear differences in how developed and enforceable each system is. Brazil presents the most visible centralized governance structure, combining a federal legal framework, CEUAS, a dedicated authority (CONCEA), national reporting mechanisms and recent sector-specific bans such as cosmetics testing. Mexico also shows a comparatively structured system, particularly through NOM-062-ZOO-1999 and the involvement of institutions such as

SENASICA and COFEPRIS, although transparency-based evidence suggests that public records, committee registration, certification, and external oversight remain incomplete. Argentina, while lacking a comprehensive national law specifically dedicated to laboratory animals, demonstrates relevant institutional and technical structures, including ANMAT rules, CONICET-linked research capacity, the National System of Animal Facilities, scientific societies, and emerging alternative-methods initiatives. Colombia, Chile, and Peru also show important but uneven advances. Colombia has incorporated legal recognition of animal sentience and welfare principles alongside a cosmetic testing ban, but implementation and public reporting remain limited. Chile has developed a fragmented framework combining general animal protection law, sectoral rules, research-funding bioethics requirements, and a cosmetic animal testing ban, but still lacks centralized reporting and fully consolidated national guidance. Peru includes provisions on animal experimentation within its general animal protection legislation, but the public visibility of its institutional implementation remains limited. The situation regarding animal experimentation in the six countries reviewed is heterogeneous, presenting persistent regulatory gaps, including the absence of harmonized national legislation, limited enforcement and oversight capacity, lack of standardized systems for reporting animal use, uneven implementation of institutional ethics committees and insufficient integration of alternative methods into regulatory frameworks.

Based on the information available, it is not possible to determine with certainty which of the six countries is most dependent on conventional animal experimentation, as public animal-use data, reporting obligations, and institutional visibility vary considerably across jurisdictions. Rather than indicating higher or lower reliance on animal use, the evidence reviewed suggests differences in the visibility, coordination, and maturity of each country's regulatory and alternative-methods ecosystem. Brazil appears to have the most visible and institutionally coordinated alternative-methods infrastructure, supported by CONCEA's regulatory role, BraCVAM's contribution to validation processes, RENAMA and several laboratories and companies working with in vitro, reconstructed tissue, organoid, microphysiological, and computational approaches. Mexico also presents a relevant dual landscape, where significant reported animal use in public institutions coexists with growing alternative-methods capacity, including 3D tissue models, in vitro toxicology, and computational approaches. In Argentina, the existence of scientific societies such as RAMA and other initiatives shows meaningful technical and institutional activity. Peru, by contrast, presents more limited publicly accessible information regarding both animal-use infrastructure and alternative-methods implementation, making it difficult to assess the actual level of institutional development.

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Moved up [3]: Mexico presents a moderately structured system with strong technical standards (e.g., NOM-062) and active agencies like SENASICA and COFEPRIS, but still relies on fragmented regulations and pending operational rules in some reforms. Chile shows an emerging precautionary framework with ethical oversight and restriction based on lack of alternatives, but weaker institutional consolidation. In contrast, Peru and Argentina appear the least integrated; Peru has a fragmented system with dispersed oversight and delayed implementation of key guidelines, while Argentina lacks a comprehensive national framework for laboratory animals and relies on outdated or partial regulations. Overall, the main regional disparities are the degree of legal centralization versus fragmentation, enforcement strength versus mainly declarative frameworks, and the level of institutional coordination, ranging from fully structured systems like Brazil to more dispersed and incomplete governance in

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Overall, the comparison suggests that the main regional disparities relate less to the formal existence of animal protection rules and more to their degree of operationalization, enforceability, institutional coordination, public reporting, and integration of alternative methods. Importantly, this assessment is limited by the uneven availability of accessible information across countries. As both authors are based in Chile, and given the difficulties of accessing complete, comparable, and updated institutional information from each jurisdiction, the analysis cannot determine with certainty the full level of institutional development in every country. Therefore, while it is possible to identify limited public information, fragmented reporting, and uneven transparency as common regional challenges, the absence of accessible information should not necessarily be interpreted as evidence that institutional structures or relevant practices do not exist.

Alternative methods available in Latin America demonstrate clear strengths, particularly in improving human relevance, increasing reproducibility, reducing ethical concerns and enabling toxicological and pharmacological screening tools. *In silico* models and computational toxicology may still require animal-based validation, especially in complex systemic processes such as chronic disease progression, immunological interactions, whole-organism toxicity, reproductive biology or long-term pharmacokinetics, where current non-animal models cannot yet fully replicate integrated physiological responses.

The disparities shown in this commentary highlight that a coordinated strengthening of institutional support, harmonization of regulatory frameworks, and systematic identification of methodological gaps are essential to enable a scientifically robust and ethically responsible transition toward the gradual replacement of animal experimentation. Importantly, such a transition must be guided not only by technical feasibility but also by the incorporation of animal sentience as an unavoidable ethical and scientific consideration in any remaining experimental use.

Disclosure statement

The authors declare the following non-financial interests: Daniela Medina Concha and Raquel Valenzuela Vilos are affiliated with Te Protejo, a non-profit organization that advocates for the adoption of alternative methods testing methods, where they hold the positions of Research and Compliance Director and Research Coordinator, respectively. Additionally, Daniela Medina Concha serves as the Secretary of the Chilean Animal Bioethics Committee. These affiliations may be perceived as non-financial interests related to the subject of this review. No other potential conflicts of interest were reported.

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Data availability statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new datasets were created. All data analyzed in this [commentary](#) are derived from publicly available resources and published literature cited within the reference list.

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